

Data Management Tools for Active Research

During active research, various tools and platforms can be used to organize your data. This page lists a non-exhaustive selection of domain-specific data management solutions that are made available by the University of Basel, or are freely available online.

Natural sciences

Data management with LabKey

- [LabKey](#) is a general purpose web-based data management platform for quantitative data. It is an open-source software developed by a commercial company specialized in clinical data management. Despite being rooted in clinical data, the platform is generic enough to suit most natural (and other quantitative) sciences. Please contact [sciCORE](#) to get started.

Microscopy image repository with OMERO

- [OMERO](#) is a client-server software for managing, visualizing and analyzing microscopy images and associated metadata. The data repository not only supports the management of microscopy image data but also allows for their visualization, annotation, archiving, sharing and export of images. OMERO supports over 120 different microscopy file formats. At the Biozentrum, an OMERO server is jointly operated by the department's [Imaging Core Facility \(IMCF\)](#) and [Biozentrum Research IT](#).

Electronic Lab Notebook (ELN)

- An ELN is a software tool that typically replicates an interface similar to a page in a paper lab notebook. In an ELN you can enter protocols, observations, notes, and other experimental data. The [Biozentrum Wiki](#) can be used as an ELN by members of the Biozentrum and other life science groups of the University of Basel. There is a multitude of other ELN tools available; the [ELN Finder](#) can help you select a suitable tool. Beware of legal, ethical and/or financial constraints when choosing an ELN.

Humanities & social sciences

Bibliographic data management with Zotero

- [Zotero](#) is a free, open-source literature management program for collecting, managing and citing various online and offline sources. It supports the editing of bibliographic information and literature lists in scientific publications. The [University Library](#) offers trainings.

Archival photo management with Tropy

- [Tropy](#) is a free, open-source application to manage, describe and organize photographs of research materials, especially archival sources. An annotation tool allows to transcribe and contextualize research data. [RISE](#) provides support and trainings.

Surveys with EvaSys

- [EvaSys](#) is suitable for the secure execution of large surveys and evaluations. It can be used for both paper-based and online surveys. The advantage lies in the various automation functions. The results of the survey can be further processed in other programs (e.g. SPSS) or summarized into any partial results. For more information and support, contact the [EvaSys Survey Services](#) of the University of Basel.

For further information about tools and platforms for research in the humanities & social sciences, contact the [RISE](#) team.

